

Paper 10

IoT as a Potential Academic Degree: The Strategies—*An Overview*

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ABSTRACT

Education System is changing rapidly with different attributes and methodologies. The general academic methodology and model is also changing rapidly. Currently educational programs are changing from the traditional settings and this includes changes in broad subject to the sub fields and emerging specializations. Further the concept of Major and Minor also been incorporated in recent past including the specialization and dual specialization. As far as Information Technology and Computing is concerned, initially only broad subjects are offered viz. Computer Science, Computer Application, Information Technology, Informatics, Information Science, ICT etc. but in recent past the traditional concept has been changed and here emerging specialization is noted such as Cloud Computing, Big Data, Internet of Things, Data Analytics, Human Computer Interaction, Robotics, Artificial Intelligence etc. Internet of Things (IoT) is emerging subject within Information Technology and Computing. In Education Systems such specializations are noted in different disciplines including Science, Management, Engineering etc. As far as India is concerned within the large number of educational institutions few are offering specializations in IoT. However there are healthy potentialities to offer educational programs in the areas Internet of Things (IoT) in Indian context in diverse disciplines and subjects. This Paper has proposed the way to introduce Internet of Things (IoT) in different angles and point of view in Indian and International context.

Keywords

Internet of Things (IoT), Information Technology, Education, Higher Degrees, Educational Curricula, Emerging Degrees

Introduction

Objective

Internet of Things (IoT): Basics

Internet of Things (IoT) as depends on internet systems, digitally connected and controlled anywhere. The IoT ultimately helps in increases efficiency, safety, security etc with applications in wider zones viz. oil & gas, manufacturing, transportation, agriculture, retail sectors etc.

Internet of Things (IoT) can be initial costly for the implementation but later on organizational cost can be reduced radically. Importantly, IoT devices can be used for the following broad areas (categories)—

- Consumer (the users).
- Commercial.
- Industrial or organizational and
- Infrastructure spaces etc.

In the areas viz. home automation & smart home development including the smart town and smart villages creation etc IoT can be considered as important and valuable.

Fig: 3.3-The gateway for IoT and its stakeholders

For the development of *Smart Home*, the IoT devices can be considered important with the applications in air conditioning, lighting, heating, security systems etc. The intelligent hub using control smart devices viz. iPhone or iOS native applications can be considered and useful in this regard. The concepts of *Smart Buildings* is also emerging which is responsible for reducing energy consumption etc.

The *old aged people* can get the benefits of IoT in the disabilities and elderly individuals. Here the technologies viz. assistive technology, voice control systems can be used in normal care and medical emergencies as well.

“Vision of Future Education”

Smarter Healthcare is another name which is can get the benefits of IoT in health related activities viz. collection, analysis of data for healthy medical informatics building and development with proper medical resources.

Remote based health monitoring and emergency services and notification systems are the core part of IoT systems including the usages of pacemakers, smart beds, patient get up, nursing informatics practice, medical follow-up etc. Furthermore introduction of ‘m-health’ is also valuable with the IoT.

In **Transportation**, as well IoT is important for different kind of communications vehicle, Smart traffic control systems, Smart and electronic toll collection, the infrastructure management and even in Human Resource Management including driver, road safety etc. The healthy transport system can be powered by IoT.

Internet of Things (IoT) based **Manufacturing** is another concern of IoT; which is responsible for identification, processing, communication of the affairs related to manufacturing of the industries also. It helps in Network control of manufacturing equipment, Healthy and rapid manufacturing, smarter supply chain systems and also Service information systems including the Smart Grid using Internet of Things (IoT). Thus the concept of Industrial Internet of Things or IIoT is gradually developing. Such and emerging services become only possible due to the increasing components in IoT; which may also applicable in AIoT (refer Fig: 4).

Fig: 3.4-Major components of IoT

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IoT and Some Possible Degrees

IoT as a Full-fledged Education in Engineering

B.Tech/B.E. (Internet of Things)
M.Tech/M.E. (Internet of Things)
Ph.D.Engg. (Internet of Things)

IoT as a Full-fledged Education in Sciences

B.Sc. / M.Sc. (Internet of Things)
B.S. / M.S. (Internet of Things)
Ph.D.-Science (Internet of Things)

IoT as a Full-fledged Education in Management

BBA (IoT and Business/ IIoT)
MBA (IoT and Business/ IIoT)
PhD-(IoT and Business/ IIoT)

IoT as a Full-fledged Education as a Specialization in Computing related Programs

BSc/MSc-Computer Science (IoT and Business/ IIoT)
BS/MS-Computer Science (IoT and Business/ IIoT)
BSc/MSc-Information Technology (IoT and Business/ IIoT)
BSc/MSc-Information Technology (IoT and Business/ IIoT)
PhD-CSE/ IT (IoT and Business/ IIoT)
